

A LOOK AT THE SOCIAL-MORAL, PHILOSOPHICAL CONCEPTS IN THE WORLD OF SHAKESPEARE AND IN HIS WORK

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6585289>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 10th May 2022

Accepted: 14th May 2022

Online: 26th May 2022

KEY WORDS

*drama, social inequality,
social thinking,
enlightenment, pathos,
emotion, observation,
culture, lust, morality*

ABSTRACT

The article analyzes the socio-ethical and philosophical concepts of Shakespeare's period and his work, the connection of his works with ancient literature and Oriental art of speech, the scope of ideas and themes put forward in his dramas. It also discusses the situation in which Eastern philosophy is in harmony with Western culture, individual freedom, and social inequality.

Three factors played a decisive role in the development of medieval literature. These are folk art, ancient culture and art, and the influence of the church. In particular, the role of folk poetry traditions is fragmentary. Labor songs, which are the oldest examples of poetry, went beyond customs and rituals in the Middle Ages and formed as an independent literary genre. Although religious superstition and bigotry prevailed for a long time, it still did not quench people's natural desire for the blessings and joys of life.

The influence of ancient culture on medieval literature is reflected in Shakespeare's King Lear, Macbeth, Hamlet, Timon of Athens, Anthony and Cleopatra, Julius Caesar, Richard III, Richard II, and Henry IV., Henry V, and King John.

In the development of English drama, the first examples of the literature of this nation appeared in the form of songs dedicated to the issues of labor, war, domestic life. Such songs, which embodied special events in the life of the people, became the basis for the creation of epic epics. In turn, they reflect the people's daily life, life mixed with joy and sorrow, dreams, hopes for the future, happiness, prosperity. In Shakespeare's dramas, positive heroes (Hamlet, Hortsio, Laert, Duncan, Banko, Macbeth, McDuff, Lennox Seward) are embodied as brave, courageous, healthy, generous, always ready to help the oppressed, to sacrifice their lives for the motherland.

For example, in the world-famous "Romeo and Juliet", love is glorified as a high divine feeling. The brave, courageous Romeo, who sacrificed in the way of his love, is honored.

In contrast, the actions of cowards, traitors, unproven, ruthless, ambitious people (Claudius, Gertrude, Polonius, Macbeth, Lady Macbeth) are ruthlessly exposed.

The play is characterized by the expression of events in folk epics, the courage of the noble Romeo, as well as the analysis of deep human feelings, qualities, friendship, devotion, which enhances the value of this artistic monument.

In turn, the drama "Romeo and Julietta" stands out among the monuments of art. Elements of realism and populism are reflected in the image and interpretation of positive images. The similarities between this work and Alisher Navoi's epic "Layli and Majnun" and the Uzbek people's epic "Tahir and Zuhra" can be seen in the character, intensity, power and aspirations of the heroes of both works. Both Romeo and Majnun are tragically killed because of the disagreement between the people, the conflict between them. At the end of the work, the conflict between the two tribes and two families at the top of the graves of the lovers ends. Romeo is shown in a highly dramatic pathos that Farhod is the victim of a lie. The love, joy, devotion and betrayal sung in Shakespeare's works are the main themes of the playwright's work. They emphasize the psychology of the heroes. Among Shakespeare's plays, Romeo and Julietta stands out. It depicts human love and worldly events, and love is sung as a result of man's natural feelings. In the work of the playwright there are features of Eastern literature, such as the praise of beauty, the pleasures of life, the thoughtful inspection of life. In works that depict the evolution of human psychology in his heart, the protagonists make accusations against the period.

Literature, in fact, means the ascension from the nafs to the heart, from the heart to the soul, from the soul to the mystery, from it to the meaning and essence. In each of these "statuses" the talented writer sees the human personality in a new light and laughs at new changes. Shakespeare has achieved all this. Literary scholar I. Hakkulov emphasizes that one of the most attractive features of Shakespeare's drama is to show the true image of man in the "mirror" of emotions, to describe the struggles of desire and destiny in the language of the situation.

When thinking about literary influence, it is impossible not to remember Dante. The influence of Oriental literature on Dante's work was specially studied by N.Kamilov.

Dante's work was strongly influenced by Eastern literature. After the Me'rojnama and the Thousand and One Nights were translated into Spanish on the orders of King Alfonso X, various legends about the Prophet Muhammad's Meroj, Eastern poetry, played a major role in the development of secular European literature.

All this is not in vain. Because the influence in all areas was also strong in the literature department. It is acknowledged that the prose examples of Eastern word art in terms of etiquette and teaching had a great influence on European literature.

Panchatantra, written in Sanskrit in the 3rd and 4th centuries, had a strong influence on European literature in the Middle Ages and the Renaissance in terms of genre, style and content. This collection of short stories, called Kalila and Dimna, was translated into Arabic in the eighth century, and then into Greek, Hebrew, Latin, Spanish, and other languages. Slovak scientist M. Galik akademik S. F. Relying on Oldenburg, he

said: "Panchatantra is the second most widely circulated work in the book world after the Bible. He influenced the development of medieval and Renaissance literature to such an extent that it cannot be compared to any other example of Oriental literature.

Indeed, no nation can ever develop in isolation from others, creating its own special culture. The centuries-old cultural ties between East and West, especially the process in the Middle Ages and the Renaissance. Confirms the idea of happiness.

The homeland of the Renaissance movement is Italy. When we talk about the Renaissance, we should first focus on the main aspects of the literature of this country. One of the greatest masters of speech in the cultural development of mankind is Dante Alighieri.

The work that sealed Dante's name in eternity, *The Divine Comedy*, consists of 33 songs (poems). This epic is further divided into parts such as "Hell", "Araf" and "Paradise", which describe the three parts of the world. The songs are written in the form of *tertsina*, i.e. trinity.

Dante used allegory and symbolism in the medieval genre of "vision" to create the *Divine Comedy*. However, the plot of "Dorulbaqo" reflects not only religious views, but also important issues related to real life. The protagonist of this work is the author Dante himself, and the epic tells the story of his birth while alive, crossing the borders of the eternal world under the guidance of the spirits of the ancient Roman poet Virgil and his lover Beatrice. It consists of a nine-story depth. Sinful spirits suffer on those floors. The lower the rank, the heavier the punishment.

Dante, the first representative of the new age, in the fourth song of "Hell", the poet embodied great people who made an invaluable contribution to the development of science, art and literature. The traveling poet meets Eastern scholars, such as Homer, Aeschylus, Sophocles, Aristotle, Plato, Socrates, Pythagoras, Heraclitus, Democritus, as well as our great ancestor Ibn Sina. The next stage of the eternal world is described in the second part of the epic "A'raf", which is located opposite the globe. The ocean separates it from the ground. There is a high mountain on the island in the middle of the ocean. The mountain has seven steps, and as it passes over them, the rebellious slaves are cleansed of sins.

During the Renaissance, genius writers also flourished in Spanish, French, and English literature. Miguel Cervantes, author of *Don Quixote*, François Rable, author of *Gargantua and Pantagruel*, great playwrights William Shakespeare, and Christopher Marlowe are proof of our point. Under the influence of the socio-political events that took place in Western Europe in the XV-XVI centuries, advanced humanistic ideas were propagated in the literature due to the peculiarities of their historical development.

In general, one of the main features of Renaissance word art is that it has a realistic content in addition to the humanistic spirit. The creators adopted the ideas of the struggle for equality and justice from ancient sources. Influence on such features of ancient literature can be seen in the works of F. Rable, Cervantes, and many tragedies of Shakespeare and Marlo.

The positive heroes of Renaissance realism embody incomparable courage and bravery. The great humanists who defended the

freedom of the individual also reflected the living spirit of the Renaissance by creating noble images who believed in their own power, the triumph of justice, fought for truth, and were pure in heart.

As far as the question of literary influence and connection is concerned, it is necessary to dwell on two contradictory but at the same time interdependent situations. We are talking about synchronous and diachronic effects here.

The Enlightenment did not consider the existing social systems and orders on Earth to be perfect. According to them, the unfavorable situation in society should be corrected or eliminated by the supreme power of man - the intellect, and ignorance should be removed from the mire of backwardness. Because although God created the universe, man has the freedom, the right, and the obligation to control it. That is why human creativity is so highly valued.

Proponents of this line have argued that human enlightenment is capable of leading the world to goodness, arguing that there is a harmony between "sociality" and "naturalness," "civilization," and "nature." Therefore, in the literature of this period, in general, in the arts in general, emphasis was placed on strengthening the material basis of culture and enlightenment, and the struggle of the human child with the forces of nature and its victory in this process, the test of human thinking.

The importance of the main aesthetic views in the Enlightenment literature is explained by the fact that the educational features of art were directed to the reconstruction of society. The fact that the writers of the English Renaissance created political-philosophical novels, philosophical stories,

dramatic works of political-moral content in the spirit of enlightenment confirms our opinion. Enlightenment writers saw literature as a tool of ideological struggle. They sought to exaggerate the courage, hard work and initiative of their positive heroes, as well as the idea of generosity. These features can be observed in the activities of major artists from different countries.

The Enlightenment opposed conditionality, artificiality, in the literature of classicism, and, unlike the classicists, appealed to the lives of ordinary people. Their innovation in literature was also evident not only in the expression of new ideas, but also in the expression of new forms. The enlighteners gave the existing shambles a unique look and a unique meaning. In particular, they raised the development of drama to a new level. Thus the demands of classicist drama on the higher (tragedy) and lower (comedy) genres were deviated from.

Representatives of this direction paid special attention to the description and analysis of the daily concerns and aspirations of the people. These qualities were vividly reflected in Shakespeare's work.

It is in the development of the novel and prose in general that a great step has been taken in the literature on theoretical and aesthetic issues due to the Enlightenment movement. New forms of epic genres appeared in fiction - educational-didactic novels, domestic novels, philosophical short stories, comic epics, etc., and thus unique methods of analysis of the human psyche were discovered.

Speaking of the great representatives of Enlightenment literature in Britain, it is worth mentioning the names of famous novelists of this country Daniel Defoe,

Samuel Richardson, Henry Fielding, Tobias George Smollett, Richard Brinsley Sheridan, poet Robert Burns. In particular, Defoe enriched the treasury of world literature with his works about the traveler Robinson Crusoe. In the first of this series of novels, the writer tells of a man who landed on a deserted island and survived because of his mind, will, ingenuity, aspirations and hard work. , skillfully described his struggle for survival.

In general, this immortal work alone is enough for the great writer to take an eternal place in the history of world literature. Defoe, who introduced the novel genre into English literature and was one of the leading intellectuals of his time, was also well known as a publicist and researcher. His scientific, creative and literary activity is wide and varied. In addition to his numerous articles and pamphlets, the author has a number of works on philosophy, economics, history, pedagogy, statistics, geography, and medicine.

As a progressive writer of his time, Defoe Robinson Crusoe was able to incorporate both the most delicate emotions, qualities, and conflicting traits of the human child into his character. The longevity of the work can be explained by the fact that the breath of labor that changes nature and society is in the depths of the inscriptions.

After this work, written in 1719, Defoe wrote The Life and Adventures of the famous Captain Singleton, as well as a sequel to Robinson Crusoe's past.

"The Adventures of Robinson Crusoe" was translated into Uzbek by Yuldash Shamsharov.

The work of Jonathan Swift, a contemporary of Defoe, also plays an important role in English literature of the Enlightenment. He

is one of the most famous critics in the history of not only English but also world literature. Swift's life and literary work cannot be imagined without turning a blind eye to the various political struggles of his time, the social realities of his native Ireland. The writer, who put the happiness of the people and the happiness of the homeland above the narrow interests of the ruling circles, took an active part in the struggle against the oppression of British colonialism, along with his patriotic colleagues for the freedom of the Irish people and country.

Although the play depicts mythical, fairy-tale-like events, it is primarily about human relationships, the intricacies of social life, political hypocrisy, and the ignorant real face of society. It ridiculed the ugly deeds and foolish customs of the rulers and those around them. This novel, which reflects the characteristics of the period, is a true generalization of English life, a critical and objective assessment of it, a reflection of the writer's attitude to the politics, science and culture of the time.

In turn, the Enlightenment movement has produced such great artists in England as Shakespeare, John Lili, Robert Green, Thomas Nash, famous for their socio-political, philosophical and literary activities. While the English Enlightenment developed in the post-revolutionary period and took a compromise with it, the movement's supporters in France emerged at a time when the struggle of the social forces against the monopoly feudal order was intensifying and strengthened, with the ultimate goal of preparing a bourgeois revolution.

Dramaturgy plays an important role in the literary heritage of the great enlightener

Shakespeare. During his short life, he managed to write 37 dramas and further enriched the treasury of world literature with his immortal works. He had a special love for theater and was engaged in drama writing for fifty-three years of his life. We have inherited such masterpieces as King Lear, Macbeth, Hamlet, Othello, Coriolan, Julius Caesar, Anthony and Cleopatra.

The idea of the great French thinker Victor Hugo Voltaire's great influence on the culture of the time: "He was more than a man" can also be applied to Shakespeare.

The role of Shakespeare's work in the success of English drama in the Renaissance is fragmentary. One of the greatest playwrights in world literature, he was famous for his plays "King Lear Barber", "Hamlet" and "Othello". In these works, the author praised human intelligence, business acumen and dexterity. In turn, he ridiculed jealous, lowly, hypocrites like Yago. His dramas also condemned social inequality.

Shakespeare's ideas had a strong influence on the social thinking and literature of many countries. He is one of those who was able to give a new spirit not only to the literature of the English Renaissance, but also to the classical word art of this people.

The influence of ancient culture on medieval literature is reflected in Shakespeare's King Lear, Macbeth, Hamlet, Timon of Athens, Anthony and Cleopatra, Julius Caesar, Richard III, Richard II, and Henry IV., Henry V, and King John. In his dramas, positive heroes (Hamlet, Hortsio, Laert, Duncan, Banko, Macbeth, McDuff, Lennox Sivard) are embodied as brave, courageous, healthy, generous, always ready to help the oppressed, to sacrifice their lives for the motherland. In Shakespeare's works, Eastern culture, science, and philosophy

were combined with Western culture. The following words of the great literary critic Mikhail Bakhtin in his book "Aesthetics of Words" are noteworthy: Every cultural event lives within boundaries. When a culture is out of bounds, it loses its support, crumbles and dries up, becomes the same, and finally dies "[1; 266].

The Renaissance paved the way for Enlightenment rhetoric [2; 379]. Let us consider the terminological meaning of this movement. The word "enlightenment" is used in a broad sense in the sense of making the people educated, enlightened, but in a narrow and clear sense it refers to the intellectual movement in the era of the rise of feudalism.

The importance of the main aesthetic views in the Enlightenment literature is explained by the fact that the educational features of art were directed to the reconstruction of society. The fact that the writers of the English Renaissance created political-philosophical novels, philosophical stories, dramatic works of political-moral content in the spirit of enlightenment confirms our opinion.

The Enlightenment opposed conditionality, artificiality, in the literature of classicism, and, unlike the classicists, appealed to the lives of ordinary people. Their innovation in literature was also evident not only in the expression of new ideas, but also in the expression of new forms. The enlighteners gave the existing shamails a unique look and a unique meaning. In particular, they raised the development of drama to a new level. Thus, the demands of classicist drama on the higher (tragedy) and lower (comedy) genres were deviated from [3; 467].

Representatives of this direction paid special attention to the description and

analysis of the daily concerns and aspirations of the people. These qualities were vividly reflected in Shakespeare's work.

In all his works, Shakespeare promoted the doctrine of the detailed depiction of life in all its intensity and contradiction as the first basis of drama, defended the theoretical principles of realistic theater and drama. The artist also proved that real drama has a wider and more possibilities than the art of painting in depicting life events, human heart and emotions, actions, deeds, characters of people of different social classes. The fate of King Lear is family and children, state and personality. , a wide range of possibilities for continuous reflection on dozens of issues, such as practice and morality, lust and conscience. So is the immortality of a work of art.

It is noteworthy that Shakespeare was a proponent of the simplicity and authenticity of dramaturgy. He raised life issues that were relevant for his time. Feudal-nobility regimes protested the ruling environment. The tragic resolution in these works, written with high pathos, sounded like a sign of sharp protest against the environment of the time.

The pinnacle of Shakespeare's work is undoubtedly Hamlet. The idea of subjugating the powerful forces of nature and the universe to the will of man, studying its laws and serving these mysteries for the benefit of mankind is embodied in the image of Hamlet.

The tragedy shows the clash of two opposing forces: Claudius and Hamlet. One of them is the enlightened, educated, honest, conscientious Hamlet is a symbol of goodness. He struggles with himself first and foremost as a human being. Another

powerful force, Claudius, embodied doubt, denial, and destruction.

Shakespeare skillfully instills in the nature and psyche of the protagonist that one of the most important phenomenal phenomena inherent in humanity is the need to think at the heart of everything. While the logic that "people need human morality based on human nature, experience, and understanding" [1; 7] defines Hamlet's worldview, Claudius is ready for any humiliation for glory and the throne.

Shakespeare's dramas focus on beauty, emotion, intuition, observation, and imagination, as opposed to the world of shadows ruled by ideas, to an interesting, full reality. excellent Because the beauty in art is the beauty that is born and re-created in the land of the soul, since the creation of the soul is higher than nature and its phenomena, the beauty in art is equally superior to the natural beauty "[4, 72].

In Shakespeare's dramas, the focus is on beauty, emotion, intuition, observation, and imagination, and appeals to an interesting, full-fledged reality as opposed to the world of shadows ruled by ideas. [5; 72].

According to the Russian thinker Chernyshevsky, it was Belinsky's works such as "Articles on Folk Literature", "Literary Dreams", "The Ball of Wisdom", "Mentsel-Goethe Critic", "Poetry of Mikhail Lermontov", "Hamlet. Shakespeare's Drama" series showed the real way in the emergence of national literature.

"You just have to write about what you know, what you know, and when you write, be sincere and honest; let the described situation burn the human heart, help to evaluate the reality, become a part of the reality experienced by the reader "[6; 44]. Hence, Shakespeare's dramas can answer

all of this. Rare works created by the playwright play an important role in the development of literary and aesthetic views

of the Renaissance artists, and these works depict life and death, joy and sorrow, happiness and tragedy side by side.

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